

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART XII

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Several phenothiazines containing methoxy, ethoxy, chloro, methyl and ethyl grouping have been synthesised with a view to testing their insecticidal activity.

The insecticidal properties of phenothiazine were discovered during an investigation of the toxicity of organic sulphur compounds to mosquito larvae (Campbell *et al.*, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1934, 27, 1176). Subsequent investigations established the effectiveness of the phenothiazine as a stomach poison against other insects, notably the codling moth though, as is characteristic with organic compounds, it is not effective against all species (Siegler and Smith, *ibid.*, 1935, 28, 772).

Fifteen phenothiazines with different substituents like alkyl, alkoxy, and halogen were prepared with a view to studying the effect of these substituents on the insecticidal activity. These alkyl, alkoxy and halogen groups have been chosen as these substituents are known to effect a marked variation in the solubility of the compounds in lipoid and water, an important factor controlling insecticidal activity.

The substituted phenothiazines were prepared by fusing sulphur and substituted diphenylamines in the presence of 1.2 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride (Ackermann, Friedländer, 1911, X, p. 144). The diphenylamines required in the above experiment were obtained by condensing acetylated aromatic amines, viz., 2-methoxy-, 4-methoxy-, 2-ethoxy-, 2-chloro- and 4-chloro-aminobenzenes with bromobenzene, ethylbromobenzene and *para*-bromotoluene in presence of freshly precipitated copper, using nitrobenzene as the solvent after the method of Goldberg (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4543) and subsequent deacetylation with dilute hydrochloric acid and ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted Diphenylamines.—The appropriate acetanilide (1 M) fused potassium carbonate (2 g.), bromobenzene (1 M) and a trace of freshly precipitated copper were taken in nitrobenzene (15 c.c.) and slowly refluxed for 15 hours. The nitrobenzene was steam-distilled and the residue was taken up in ether. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the ether the acetyldiphenylamine was refluxed with ethanol and HCl (conc.) and made alkaline with caustic soda solution when the substituted diphenylamine was obtained as a dark-coloured solid, which was crystallised from ethanol. The m.p., yield and percentage of nitrogen are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Diphenylamines.	M.P	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
2-Methoxy-	71°	80.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO	6.91	7.04
4-Methoxy-	79°	85.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO	6.85	7.04
4-Ethoxy-	61°	75.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO	6.70	6.50
2-Chloro-	65°	80.2	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NCl	6.10	6.80
4-Chloro-	61°	80.2	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NCl	6.00	6.80
2-Methoxy-4'-methyl-	50°	75.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO	6.10	6.60
4-Methoxy-4'-methyl-	55°	75.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO	6.15	6.60
4-Ethoxy-4'-methyl-	69°	81.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO	5.98	6.14
2-Chloro-4'-methyl-	80°	81.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NCl	6.10	6.40
4-Chloro-4'-methyl-	85°	96.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NCl	6.00	6.40
2-Methoxy-4'-ethyl	56°	74.9	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO	6.02	6.16
4-Methoxy-4'-ethyl-	58°	79.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO	5.98	6.16
4-Ethoxy-4'-ethyl-	59°	69.7	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO	5.24	5.81
2-Chloro-4'-ethyl-	70°	65.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NCl	5.95	6.08
4-Chloro-4'-ethyl-	75°	70.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NCl	5.88	6.08

Substituted Phenothiazines.—The phenothiazines were obtained by following the method of Ackermann (*loc. cit.*).

The appropriate diphenylamine (1 M), sulphur (1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.2 M) were heated to 140-50° till the mixture had attained a molten state. When H₂S ceased to evolve, the temperature of the bath was raised to 160° and kept for half an hour at that temperature. The melt was washed several times with hot water and the residue was dissolved in ethanol and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the ethanol, solid phenothiazine separated out. It was crystallised from ethanol. The m.p., yield and percentages of sulphur are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Phenothiazines.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1-Methoxy-	190°	70.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NSO	13.63	13.97
3-Methoxy-	200°	75.2	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NSO	13.57	13.97
3-Ethoxy-	180°	82.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NSO	12.76	13.17
1-Chloro-	175°	79.5	C ₁₂ H ₉ NSCl	13.42	13.71
3-Chloro-	188°	74.5	C ₁₂ H ₉ NSCl	13.34	13.71
1-Methoxy-7-methyl-	200°	70.1	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NSO	12.94	13.61
3-Methoxy-7-methyl-	210°	75.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NSO	12.62	13.61
3-Ethoxy-7-methyl-	190°	70.3	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NSO	12.24	12.45
1-Chloro-7-methyl-	185°	70.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NSCl	12.78	12.92
3-Chloro-7-methyl-	190°	75.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NSCl	12.36	12.12
1-Methoxy-7-ethyl-	205°	74.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NSO	11.96	12.45
3-Methoxy-7-ethyl-	220°	65.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NSO	12.14	12.45
3-Ethoxy-7-ethyl-	195°	70.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NSO	11.53	11.81
1-Chloro-7-ethyl-	198°	78.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NSCl	12.08	12.24
3-Chloro-7-ethyl-	200°	75.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NSCl	11.86	12.24